

Quantification of Heat Loads for Rotating Detonation Combustors with Gas Turbine Conditions

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Rotating Detonation Combustors (RDC) offer a high-power density compared to other combustors. Although they must overcome many challenges to be integrated into a gas turbine (GT), it is certainly a promising solution for increasing cycle efficiency. Among the many challenges, cooling the RDC is one of the most predominant due to the high heat loads generated by the combustion process. Most of the available numerical and experimental data in the literature about RDC heat loads are obtained for laboratory conditions (i.e. at atmospheric pressure). However, to design a cooling system for an RDC that allows for its sustainable operation and aids its integration into GT engines, a quantification of the heat loads of an RDC operating at conditions representative of GT is necessary. The presence of a detonation wave/boundary layer interaction and a small annulus width leads to a high heat transfer when compared to a conventional GT combustor. This paper describes the numerical models and tools to estimate the heat flux and heat transfer coefficient of an RDC that would be relevant for setting cooling requirements in practical systems. The simulations are conducted using Ansys Fluent utilizing a single-step reaction mechanism. Since the flow in some parts of the RDC is supersonic, the compressible boundary relations are used to model the heat transfer. Integral boundary layer methods are employed to build a tool which uses 2D distributions of integral quantities to obtain the heat flux. A global heat transfer model is built using these simulations as a reference. The results have shown that the heat transfer in the RDC is enhanced by the presence of a blockage at the combustor outlet. The effects on the flow field are associated with an increase in chamber pressure and detonation strength, determining an increment of the heat transfer coefficient to the liner walls.

Abbreviations

BR	Blockage Ratio
GT	Gas Turbine
OS	Oblique Shock
PGC	Pressure Gain Combustion

RDC Rotating Detonation Combustor

Nomenclature

θ_{tr}	Momentum Thickness (-)
\mathbf{m}_i	mass flow (kg/s)
\mathbf{Q}_{wall}	Wall Heat Flux (W/m ²)
γ	ratio of specific heats (-)

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ν	kinematic viscosity (m^2/s)	St	Stanton Number (-)
ρ	Density (kg/m^3)	T	Static Temperature (K)
τ_H	Wall Shear Stress ($kg/(m^2.s)$)	U	Injection velocity (m/s)
A	Area (m^2)	u	Velocity (m/s)
a	Sound Speed (m/s)	Subscripts	
c_f	Skin friction coefficient (-)	0	Total quantities
H_i	Shape Factor (-)	aw	adiabatic
HTC	Convective Heat Transfer Coefficient (W/m^2K)	e	Static quantities at exit of the boundary layer
h	Enthalpy (J/kg)	fp	Flat plate
M	Mach Number (-)	P	Plenum
Pr	Prandtl Number (-)	ref	Reference or Recovery quantities
P	Pressure (Pa)	w	Wall
R	ratio of specific heats (-)		

I. Introduction

INCREASING the overall efficiency of the Gas Turbine (GT) engine is essential to reducing the fuel consumption, and hence specific pollutant emissions. Increasing even a decimal amount of efficiency is a difficult task for the GT engineers. Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC) technologies, when integrated into gas turbine engines, have been shown to improve the overall efficiency[1]. The Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC) is considered to be one of the most advantageous implementations of PGC because of lower unsteadiness and easier integration with no moving parts [2].

There are several configurations of rotating detonation combustors, with different shapes [3] and sizes [4–6]. One of the most used configuration is a circular RDC where the combustion process happens in a small annulus with fuel and air supplied from the head end and the burnt products are expanded out of the aft end. The detonation wave continuously loops around this circular annulus. A sufficiently high mass flow rate of detonable mixture is required to sustain the detonation wave due to its high consumption speed. The flow field of an annular RDC is shown in Figure 1. This figure represents the TU Berlin test rig which is designed to operate at a maximum thermal power of 2 MW. The combustor operates with hydrogen and air with an annulus width of 7.6 mm and an outer wall diameter is 90 mm. The fuel enters axially to the combustor while air enters radially in a jet-in-cross flow configuration. The fuel enters through 100 fuel injectors with a diameter of 0.5 mm and the air enters through an annular radial air gap injectors with a width of 1 mm. The structure of the flow field is characterized by a detonation front with a trailing oblique shock. This oblique shock extends to the outlet and travels with the same speed in the laboratory frame of reference as the detonation, however the shock strength and relative Mach number is significantly lower. The bulk flow exiting the combustor is mainly axial with minimal tangential component. This configuration presents essentially two unique regions in the combustion chamber with respect to consideration of the cooling requirements. One characterized by rotation of the detonation front, the other, further downstream, characterized by burnt gas expansion and the passage of the oblique shock wave.

Thermal management and optimization of cooling systems for GT engines is important because it has an impact on overall efficiency. Quantifying the heat loads is essential to estimating cooling requirements. RDCs, due to a small annulus width, highly compressible and highly unsteady flow, and high temperature gases very close to the walls, results in peak heat transfer levels at least an order of magnitude greater than the conventional GT combustors. Therefore, the study of the heat transfer mechanism(s) is important for the characterization of these heat loads.

Several previous research works have dealt with the evaluation of the thermal load in RDC, both experimentally and numerically. Early investigations on the topic have been performed by Theuerkauf et al.[8–11]. This series of investigations considered a water cooled RDE and, by means of experiments and numerical simulations, investigated both instantaneous and average heat fluxes. The results indicated heat flux peaks of $25MW/m^2$. However, averaged results indicated much smaller values. Experimental results showed an almost constant averaged heat flux along the axial direction of the RDC close to $1MW/m^2$, while numerical results indicated an increasing and then decreasing profile of the average heat flux along the walls of the RDC, with a maximum value of $2.5MW/m^2$. Later, in 2017 and 2018, Meyer et al. [12, 13] investigated the impact of several parameters on the resulting heat flux by means of heat flux gauges. Those results showed a sensitivity of the heat flux on the annulus width, the equivalence ratio considered, and the mass flux. Specifically, it was shown that the heat flux continues increasing up to values of equivalence ratio of 1.25.

Furthermore, [12] showed that the heat flux increases with increasing wave speed, independently of the mass flow considered. All of these results have indicated a bulk heat flux well below $0.5MW/m^2$. However, higher heat flux values up to $5MW/m^2$ have been measured by Goto et al.[14]. This study showed that the chamber pressure was roughly

Fig. 1 Schematic of rotating detonation combustor obtained from [7].

proportional to the mass flux at the outlet restriction. The results indicated an almost linear relation between the mass flux and the measured heat flux, reaching a maximum close to $5 \text{ MW}/\text{m}^2$ for a chamber pressure of 400 kPa which was obtained for a mass flux of $\approx 210 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s})$. Further investigation on the topic has been carried out by Stevens et al.[15][16] where measurements of bulk heat flux have been performed considering the instantaneous heat release and the mass flux as variables. The results have indicated an increase of heat flux up to around $1.5 \text{ MW}/\text{m}^2$ associated with a change of detonation mode within the combustor, itself driven by changes in the provided mass flux. In addition, the results indicated an increase in heat transfer coefficient driven by an increase of passage frequency of the detonation wave.

On the numerical side of the research effort, fewer results are available. Roy et al.[17, 18] developed models for the assessment of the RDC wall temperature, but required the definition of a heat transfer coefficient on the cold side a priori. Braun et al.[19] investigated the wall heat flux along the axial direction of the RDE by means of a reduced order model. Their results have indicated a steep increase in the heat flux, with values up to $10 \text{ MW}/\text{m}^2$, increasing for higher pressure of the fresh gases being considered.

These results indicate that as long as an RDC is operated at ambient conditions, i.e. the pressure of the fresh gases is the same as the pressure of the laboratory in which the RDC is operated, the measured heat flux is relatively low, often below $1 \text{ MW}/\text{m}^2$, a value comparable with conventional gas turbine combustor. However, as soon as the pressure in the combustion chamber is increased, the resultant heat flux rapidly increases, showing a strong correlation between the chamber pressure and the thermal load. Therefore, before an RDC can be integrated into a GT, it is necessary to understand how the thermal load varies under representative operating conditions. Gas turbine operations are associated with elevated pressure in the combustion chamber and with the presence of the Nozzle Guide Vanes (NGV) downstream of the combustor, determining an outlet restriction.

To experimentally account for high pressure, several options can be applied. The simplest is way to achieve a pressure rise is by imposing an area restriction, as shown in Figure 2. The ratio A_r/A_c in the figure represents the area restriction ratio, where A_r is the actual area of the combustor outlet and A_c is the area of the combustor annulus. The percentage of blocked area can be obtained using Blockage Ratio (BR) defined as $1 - A_r/A_c$. BR of 0% represents no restriction while BR of 25% represents a 25% area blockage. In the present study, the latter approach will be implemented numerically, providing useful results for the understanding of the physical mechanisms associated with an increased thermal load associated with the operating of RDC operating at conditions representative of a GT.

In the current work, the quasi-3D numerical analysis of a RDC with outlet restrictions are performed. Using compressible boundary layer correlations, a tool is built to obtain the map of heat loads. The work concludes with a detailed analysis of heat load variations as a function of outlet area restrictions. Finally, a global heat transfer model is built using the CFD simulations.

Fig. 2 TU Berlin RDC with outlet restrictions. Adapted from [20].

II. Heat Load Calculation Methodology

The flow field of an RDC includes compressible flow with shock waves and high temperature gases closer to the wall. The strong interaction of the detonation wave and shock wave with the wall is expected to enhance the heat transfer leading to a higher thermal load. To model the heat transfer of such flow fields, a compressible boundary layer relation is required. The skin friction coefficient corrected for compressible flows shown in Equation 1 is used to derive the relation for boundary layer momentum thickness (Equation 2). The Stanton number relation, shown in Equation 4 is used to model the heat transfer. These relations are used by Braun et al. [19] to model the heat transfer of an RDC.

The two dimensional RDC flow field is divided into numerous axial one dimensional arrays spanning from injectors till the outlet. The boundary layer momentum thickness is obtained by integrating the transformed turbulent boundary layer relation shown in Equation 2 on the one dimensional array. The "B" in the momentum thickness term is obtained from Equation 3 where $H_{i,fp}$ is the shape factor of a boundary layer. For a turbulent boundary layer it varies from 1.1 to 1.3. The Stanton number and wall heat flux are computed using Equation 4 and 5. To compute the reference enthalpy and recovery enthalpy for the heat flux calculations Equations 6 and 7 are used. After obtaining heat loads for each one dimensional array all the arrays are stacked together to obtain the complete two dimensional distribution of RDC heat loads.

$$c_f \equiv \frac{\tau_H}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_e u_e^2} = 0.246e^{-1.561H_1} \left(\frac{M_e a_0 \theta_{tr}}{\nu_0} \right)^{-0.268} \left(\frac{T_e}{T_{ref}} \right)^{0.732} \left(\frac{T_e}{T_0} \right)^{0.268} \quad (1)$$

$$\theta_{tr}^{1.2155} = \frac{0.01173}{\left(\frac{a_0}{\nu_0} \right)^{0.2155} M_e^{B+0.2155}} \int_0^x M_e^B \frac{\left(\frac{T_e}{T_{ref}} \right)^{0.732}}{\left(\frac{T_0}{T_e} \right)^{3.268}} dx \quad (2)$$

$$B = 4.2 + 1.2155H_{i,fp} \left(\frac{h_w}{h_0} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

$$St = \frac{0.123e^{-1.151H_{i,fp}} \left(\frac{T_e}{T_{ref}} \right)^{0.732}}{\left(\frac{T_0}{T_e} \right)^{0.268} \left(\frac{M_e a_0 \theta_{tr}}{\nu_0} \right)^{0.268}} Pr_{ref}^{-2/3}, \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{wall} = St \rho_e u_e (h_{aw} - h_w). \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{h_{ref}}{h_e} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{h_w}{h_e} + 1 \right) + 0.22 \left(\frac{h_{aw}}{h_e} - 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{h_{aw}}{h_e} = 1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_e^2 (Pr)_{ref}^{2/3} \quad (7)$$

The time and phase locked average heat flux distribution on the outer wall of the TUB RDC is shown in Figure 3a. These distributions are obtained by means of high fidelity LES simulations performed by Nassini et al. [7] using AVBP solver by utilising isothermal wall boundary conditions. The highest heat transfer is observed to be in the region of the detonation where there is an occurrence of greater heat release. The presence of an oblique shock enhances the heat transfer in the post detonation region due to the shock wave boundary layer interaction and heat release due to deflagration. Due to the injection scheme used, the inner wall experiences a reduction in heat flux because of the fresh reactants refill which is at a lower temperature than the burnt gases. Furthermore, due to the three dimensionality effect of the combustion process, the hot gases are closer to the outer wall leading to a lower heat transfer along the inner wall. From the flow field of the RDC, obtained at closer proximity to the outer wall with high fidelity LES, the heat transfer methodology expressed above is applied to obtain the heat flux distribution shown in Figure 3b. The heat transfer model provides similar results when compared to the LES results. The circumferentially averaged heat flux of both outer wall and inner wall obtained from LES and the model is shown in Figure 3c. A good agreement is observed between the LES results and the boundary layer model applied on the LES flow fields. Although the model under predicts the heat transfer in the detonation region, the global average values remains similar. The shape factor $H_{i,fp}$ of 1.2 was used for obtaining the heat flux.

Fig. 3 (a) Wall heat-flux contour obtained from LES, (b) wall heat-flux contour obtained using the 2D model and (c) circumferentially-averaged heat-flux validation plot for BR = 0.

Heat loads expressed in terms of heat transfer coefficient (HTC) and gas temperature is essential for performing any kind of cooling requirement analysis or for further heat transfer analysis. Heat flux is dependent on the wall temperature which is again a function of the cold side boundary condition. However, HTC is independent of wall temperature as it is solely a function of flow field density, velocity, hot gas properties and its temperature. Experimentally obtaining the heat flux by measuring the hot gas properties is difficult. Moreover, it requires the RDC to be in thermal equilibrium which is not possible for an uncooled RDC. With numerical simulations, gas properties are easily available and it is easier to use boundary layer models to compute the the heat flux and HTC. To obtain the convective HTC, the classical formulation of heat transfer is applied: $HTC = \dot{q}/(T_{gas} - T_{wall})$ where \dot{q} is obtained from Equation 5 which is dependent on wall temperature. Hence, it has to be iterated with the wall temperature to obtain the gradient which in turn provides the HTC. The resulting HTC and gas temperature is shown in Figure 4. The HTC follows the same trend as the heat flux. It increases in the detonation region, reaching a maximum at the triple point, and then decreases downstream along the axial length. While the gas temperature remains almost constant throughout the axial length, except in the detonation region where the gas temperature reduces because of the refilling fresh gases.

Fig. 4 (a) HTC and (b) Gas temperature along the outer wall.

III. Numerical Methodology

The commercial software ANSYS Fluent was used to perform the calculations of an unrolled two dimensional RDC geometry. Fluent has already been tested by Escobar et al. [21] for performing two-dimensional RDC simulation. The dimensions of the numerical grid are based on the TU Berlin RDC shown in Figure 2. The length of the considered domain is 110 mm representing the length of the TU Berlin combustion cavity and the width is 289 mm corresponding to the mean perimeter. There are two ways of increasing the chamber pressure. The first method is to specify an average outlet pressure as a boundary condition. This method was used by Escobar et al. [21] however implementing this method is a tedious task and when tested did not provide a promising result. Implementing this method for an RDC flow field is complicated because of the presence of the oblique shock. This feature affects the numerical convergence since a non reflecting boundary condition would be required to correctly impose a specified back pressure. In the second method, the outlet area is changed to increase the chamber pressure which is similar to experiments and performs better numerically. To account for outlet restriction numerically, a quasi three dimensional mesh (i.e the thickness of the domain discretized with just one cell) is needed as depicted in Figure 5. The sizing of the quasi three dimensional grid is based on the previous studies performed by Nassini et al. [7]. Mesh sizing of 200 μm both in X and Y coordinates while a cell size of 7.6 mm in Z coordinate was utilised to perform the numerical analysis by implementing various exit widths.

Fig. 5 Schematic of the mesh with outlet section used for simulations.

A single step reaction mechanism developed by Nassini et al. [7] is utilized to model the detonation combustion. Premixed hydrogen - air mixtures are used for simulations. Navier-Stokes equations are solved with a pressure-based solver without any turbulence models. The injection scheme uses a micro injectors model: i.e. each cell in the inlet plane acts as an injector. Two injection schemes were tested. The first approach uses a velocity inlet boundary condition where the velocity in each cell is governed by the pressure difference between the adjacent cell of the injector and the set plenum pressure. The ideal gas Mach number relations are used to obtain the value of the velocity in each cell of the injection plane. The second approach employs mass sources to inject the fuel rather than a boundary condition. In this case the inlet is set as a wall boundary condition. The mass source approach requires mass, momentum, and energy

values to be provided for each cell. The mass flow is obtained from Equation 8 where P_p and T_p are the set plenum pressure and temperature, M is the Mach number obtained with the velocity relation shown in Equation 9 where U_i and P_i are the velocity and static pressure at i 'th node. The flow fields of RDC obtained with mass source injection scheme represented in terms of static temperature is shown in Figure 6a along with the temperature contour obtained closer to the outer wall using LES simulation, shown in Figure 6b. These contours are obtained for the same mass flux which corresponds to $290 \text{ kg/m}^2/\text{s}$. The LES simulation detects deflagration burning in the refill region closer to the outer wall. However, the quasi 3D simulations underpredicts the deflagration burning due to the limitations of the modeling strategy. The circumferentially averaged wall heat flux obtained using quasi 3D simulations by applying the Stanton number correlations is compared with outer and inner wall averaged wall heat flux obtained using LES in Figure 6c. The quasi 3D plus correlations have a good agreement with the LES simulations. Except in the refill region the quasi 3D under predicts the heat flux due to the absence of deflagration burring in the refill region.

$$\dot{m}_i = \frac{A P_p}{\sqrt{T_p}} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R}} M \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M^2 \right)^{-\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}} \quad (8)$$

$$U_i = \sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{\gamma - 1} R T_p \left[1 - \left(\frac{P_i}{P_p} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \right]} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 6 Static temperature contour obtained using (a) Quasi 3D simulation and (b) LES and (c) Circumferentially averaged wall heat flux plot comparing LES and Quasi 3D.

IV. Impact of Blockage Ratio

An RDC integrated into a gas turbine has to operate at higher thermal power and elevated chamber pressure. The influence of chamber pressure on the heat loads experienced by the RDC operating at constant thermal power has to be quantified to build the global heat transfer models which are used for calculating the cooling requirements. The chamber pressure can be increased by varying the BR as shown in Figure 2. The numerical methodology mentioned in Section III was used to obtain the flow fields for performing the heat transfer analysis. The total temperature contour for different BR is shown in Figure 7 for a mass flux of $500 \text{ kg/m}^2/\text{s}$ and highlights the obtained density gradient. For an

RDC without restriction (i.e BR = 0) depicted in Figure 7a the flow field includes a detonation wave with a height of 0.03 m and an oblique shock extending to the outlet. Whereas with a restriction, shown in Figure 7b and 7c, the height of the detonation decreases to 0.029 m for BR = 25 and 0.023 m for BR = 50. Furthermore, for these blocked cases, the oblique shock reflects from the outlet and creates a secondary wave that impacts the injectors. These secondary shocks play a role in increasing the heat loads of the RDC. To further assess the influence of the shock waves on the overall heat loads, a numerical simulation was performed for a BR of 25 with two wave operating mode shown in Figure 7d. The two waves are obtained by initialising with two ignition kernels.

Fig. 7 Temperature contour obtained for different Blockage Ratio.

Based on the four blockage ratio conditions shown in Figure 2, the heat load methodology mentioned in Section II was applied. The obtained circumferentially averaged HTC and gas temperature is shown in Figure 8. Increasing the blockage increases the chamber pressure from nominally 2.4 bar at BR = 0, to 3.1 bar for BR = 25 to 5.0 bar at the highest blockage of BR = 50. This causes the compression of refill gases to form a dense mixture in the refill region which results in the reduction in the refill height and hence the reduction in detonation height shown in Figure 2. Due to the denser detonable mixture, the strength of the detonation i.e. the detonation shock strength increases providing more heat release in detonation region. This increase in detonation strength causes a stronger interaction with the wall leading to an increase in heat transfer in the detonation region. As depicted in Figure 8a, for all the BR the highest heat transfer occurs at the triple point, which moves axially upstream as BR increases. Before the peak there is a reduction in HTC because of the cooling provided by the fresh gases. For BR of 0, the highest HTC is located at the axial position of 0.03 m and for BR of 50 it shifts to 0.019 m. These HTC values are obtained for the same mass flux, ensuring that the thermal power remains constant for comparability. The increase in the magnitude of HTC corresponds with the heat load change, namely due to the reduction in refill area plus a stronger detonation. The gas temperature plays a minimal role as it remains constant after the triple point for all the cases as shown in Figure 8b.

The influence of the refill area and the number of detonations waves on the circumferentially averaged HTC was studied by comparing two wave and a single wave mode for BR 25 with same mass flux. In two wave mode the detonation wave heights are half of the single wave which assures that the overall refill area combining the two waves remains the same as the single wave. In the plot of circumferentially averaged HTC the triple point is at 0.01 m for the two wave case and the magnitude is greater than the single wave. This means the presence of two detonation waves increases the overall heat transfer. Similar to the other results, the downstream levels of HTC and temperature remain nearly the same for one and two waves.

The local variation of HTC is extremely important for designing an optimised cooling system for RDC. However, for estimating the entire cooling requirement for performing cycle analysis, an estimate of the global HTC is necessary. The global HTC was obtained by axially averaging the circumferentially averaged HTC. The global HTC for BR 0, 25, and

Fig. 8 Circumferentially-averaged (a) HTC and (b) Gas temperature for BR = 0, 25 and 50.

50 correspond to 2316, 2810, and 4111 W/m^2K , respectively. For BR 25 with two waves, an increase of 7% in global HTC is observed. To characterise the variation of global HTC with mass flux, numerous simulations are performed for

Fig. 9 Variation of (a) Chamber pressure, (b) Oblique shock pressure, (c) Global HTC with respect to mass flux and (d) Variation of c_1 with BR.

the same BR configurations by varying chamber mass flux. A mass flux range of 300 to 700 kg/m^2s was chosen for the current analysis. The variation of chamber pressure, maximum oblique shock pressure, and global HTC for different BR is plotted across the mass flux range in Figure 9. As discussed earlier, the chamber pressure and shock strength influences the heat transfer. Both chamber pressure and shock pressure increases with mass flux as shown in Figure 9a and 9b.

A global heat transfer model, required for cycle efficiency analysis to compute the cooling requirements, can be built using the classical Dittus and Boelter equation expressed in terms of Reynolds number and Prandtl number [14]. The Dittus and Boelter equation expressed in terms of mass flux is shown in Equation 10 where L is the channel width, $\frac{\dot{m}}{A}$ is the mass flux, c_1 , n , and m are the constants. The constants m and n are specified as 0.8 and 0.4, respectively. Prandtl number, viscosity, and thermal conductivity are calculated using Sutherland formula. The gas temperature is chosen to be half of CJ temperature following the method of Randall et al. [22] and was obtained through SDToolbox . The constant c_1 varies for each BR since HTC changes with the chamber pressure.

$$HTC_{global} = \frac{c_1 k Pr^n}{\mu^m} L^{m-1} \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{A} \right)^m \quad (10)$$

The global HTC obtained using Equation 10 is shown in Figure 9c utilizing the constant c_1 obtained from data fits for each BR as provided in Figure 9d. The Global HTC follows the same trend as the chamber pressure. As the area restriction increases, the chamber pressure increases along with the density promoting more heat transfer. For two wave mode the presence of two detonation waves increases the chamber pressure but decreases the maximum shock pressure. In addition, the presence of two detonation waves increases the heat transfer, indeed the global HTC for BR 25 with two waves is always greater than BR 25 in single wave mode.

The Nusselt number obtained for each BR case is plotted in Figure 10. For the Dittus and Bolter relation, the value of c_1 is 0.023. The increase of c_1 for an increase in BR shows the influence or sensitivity of flow field variation on the global HTC for an RDC. The variation of the Nusselt number for the same Reynolds number with varying BR suggests that the change of detonation height, shown in Figure 7, is responsible for increasing the heat transfer. An increase in BR is indeed increasing the area exposed to the hot gases along with the increase in chamber pressure.

Fig. 10 Nusselt number plot.

V. Conclusion

Estimation of heat loads are required for designing and optimising the cooling systems for RDC. There is not much data available in the literature concerning heat loads in RDCs, especially under gas turbine conditions. To start to understand this problem better, the TU Berlin RDE geometry was used as the baseline. Three different outlets were created; the first with no restriction and then two others with restricted outlet areas. A tool was built using compressible boundary layer relations for calculating the heat transfer of high speed flows to obtain the heat loads of the RDC with these outlet restrictions. Lastly, a global heat transfer model was built by applying classical formulation to the CFD results. The variation of the constants with the blockage ratio was obtained by data fits. The current results reveal that the presence of the outlet restriction increase the heat transfer to the RDC walls. This is due to the increase in chamber

pressure within the RDC leading to a lower fill height in the refill region and an increase in detonation strength. The stronger shock waves increase the local heat transfer in the detonation region causing an overall increase in the heat transfer to RDC walls. Furthermore, the outlet restriction produces additional reflected shock in the RDC chamber. Operating the RDC in a two wave mode further increase the heat transfer due to the multiple shock waves and reduction in refill area. This had the additional effect of increasing the local heat transfer in the detonation region, albeit the downstream levels of HTC remained constant.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956803.

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